

Kinetics and Mechanism of Silver(I) catalysed Oxidation of Substituted Carboxylic Acids (Mucic and Benzilic Acids) by Peroxydisulphate Ion

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The kinetics of Ag^{I} catalysed oxidation of mucic and benzilic acids by $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ ion has been investigated in dioxane—conductivity water system using the same concentration of dioxane in each kinetic run. In both the cases, the reaction is found to be first order in $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and in the catalyst Ag^{I} , and zero order in the substrate. The energy parameters determined in the case of both the acids show a close similarity and the reaction is characterised by a large negative value of entropy of activation $\Delta S^\ddagger$. The reaction exhibits negative salt-effect of the exponential type and specific inhibitory effect. The reaction is also inhibited by the presence of allyl acetate. The products of oxidation identified are trihydroxyglutaric acid and benzophenone in the case of mucic and benzilic acids, respectively, alongwith the liberation of CO_2 . The uncatalysed oxidation of mucic acid appears to be difficult. A radical chain mechanism has been proposed and rate expression derived in consideration with the above observations.

THE literature reveals that the oxidation of substituted acids specially α -hydroxy acids as mandelic¹, lactic², malic³ and atrolactic acids has been studied by different oxidising agents besides $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ ion. However, the mechanism of most of the reactions does not appear to be satisfactory and a general agreement has not been achieved so far. The concept of stepwise transfer of electron from reductant to oxidant with respect to unstable valency states has been the basis of the mechanism proposed.

Regarding Ag^{I} catalysed oxidation by $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ ion, the most probable reaction as suggested by different workers^{4,5,6} is

The rate determining step is an oxidative decarboxylation in the substituted acids producing simultaneously a free radical. In such acids, according to Richardson and Wiberg⁷, the C—H bond is not broken and the formation of CO_2 is due to free radical $\dot{\text{C}}\text{OOH}$ created during the reaction. Waters and Levesley⁸ have stressed over the cleavage of the C—C bond and formation of the R— $\dot{\text{C}}\text{OH}$ free radical, finally giving rise to the free radical $\dot{\text{C}}\text{OOH}$. Hence, a detailed kinetic study of the Ag^{I} catalysed oxidation of mucic and benzilic acids has been carried out by us to ascertain the above views, the results of which are reported in this paper.

Experimental

All the compounds and reagents used were either of E. Merck (G.R.) or AnalaR grade Both

mucic and benzilic acids, being less soluble in aqueous medium at 35°, were dissolved in dioxane—conductivity water keeping the same concentration, i.e. 8% (v/v) of dioxane, in each kinetic run throughout the course of the study of oxidation of the acids. The unreacted $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ was estimated using iodometric method as suggested by Khulbe and Srivastava⁹.

Results

Order of reaction: The order of reaction was determined by applying Vant Hoff's differential method. It was observed that the reaction is first order in $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ ion, zero order in case of both mucic and benzilic acids, and first order in the catalyst Ag^{I} .

From Table 1, it is evident that the value of the specific reaction rate decreases with the increase of the concentration of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ but the value increases at constant $[\text{K}^+]$ as shown in Table 2. This gives an indication that the decrease in first order rate

$[\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8]$ M	Mucic acid $k(\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1})$	Benzilic acid $k(\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1})$	$k_2(\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1})$
0.005	13.48	35.05	1.79
0.0075	12.28	31.78	1.53
0.01	11.85	30.65	1.44
0.015	11.09	27.52	1.26
0.02	10.51	24.18	1.20

k_2 =Net specific rate for oxidation of organic substrate. k_1 =Specific reaction rate for the self decomposition of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$.

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TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF $[K_2S_2O_8]$ AT CONSTANT $[K^+]$
 $[\text{Acid}] = 0.01 \text{ M}$, $[\text{AgNO}_3] = 0.001 \text{ M}$, $\text{Temp} = 35^\circ$

$[K_2S_2O_8]$ M	$[K_2SO_4]$ M	Mucic acid $k(\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1})$	Benzilic acid $k(\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1})$
0.005	0.045	6.58	17.97
0.01	0.04	8.12	20.72
0.015	0.035	9.21	23.03
0.02	0.03	11.01	26.48

constant (Table 1) may be due to the inhibitory effect of K^+ ions in the reaction,

 TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF $[\text{ACID}]$
 $[K_2S_2O_8] = 0.01 \text{ M}$, $[\text{AgNO}_3] = 0.001 \text{ M}$, $\text{Temp} = 35^\circ$

$[\text{Acid}]$ 10^3 M	Mucic acid $k(\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1})$	Benzilic acid $k(\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1})$
0.10	10.07	29.72
0.25	10.36	29.88
0.30	—	29.97
0.50	10.12	29.64
0.75	11.62	30.15
1.00	11.85	30.65
1.50	—	30.42

The study of the variation of the concentration of the acids (Table 3) gives an indication that there is no significant and appreciable change in the specific reaction rate. The rate may be assumed to be independent of the concentrations of both the acids as the overall reaction follows first order kinetics.

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

 $[K_2S_2O_8] = 0.01 \text{ M}$, $[\text{AgNO}_3] = 0.001 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Acid}] = 0.01 \text{ M}$

Acid	Temp. coef.	ΔE kcal mol^{-1}	A $\times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3$ $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	ΔG kcal mol^{-1}	ΔH kcal mol^{-1}
Mucic acid (M.A.)	1.76	11.56	31.91	-40.03	23.56	10.96
Benzilic acid (B.A.)	1.72	10.20	8.93	-42.51	22.70	9.51

The two reactions were studied at five different temperatures (25–40°), and the energy parameters evaluated are presented in Table 4.

A close similarity in the values of the energy of activation, free energy of activation, enthalpy change and entropy of activation, in both the cases gives an indication to the fact that both the reactions follow a similar path of oxidation (Figs. 1 and 2). The large negative value of the entropy of activation in the reactions supports the formation of activated complex with two oppositely charged ions.

 Fig. 1. Plot of $1/T$ vs $\log k$: (O) M.A., and (●) B.A.

 Fig. 2. Plot of $1/T$ vs $\log k_r/(kT/h)$: (O) M.A., and (●) B.A.

Salt-effect: The salt-effect (as observed by using K_2SO_4) is found to be negative and of primary exponential type in both the cases (Fig. 3, showing straight lines by plotting $\log k$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$). This also suggests the formation of activated complex between two oppositely charged ions. The slopes of the curves in mucic and benzilic acids are -1.83 and -1.10, respectively. The specific inhibitory effect of different cations follows a similar order in both the reactions, $K^+ > Na^+ > Zn^{2+} > Mg^{2+} > Al^{3+}$. There is decrease of rate constant in the presence of allyl acetate, and the inhibitory effect is due to its polymerisation by capturing $SO_4^{\cdot-}$ radical created by the catalytic decomposition of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ion.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: It was observed that in the case of mucic acid, one mole of the acid required two moles of $K_2S_2O_8$ for its oxidation while one mole of benzilic acid required

Fig. 8. Plot of $\sqrt{\mu}$ vs $\log k$: (O) M.A., and (●) B.A.

one mole of potassium peroxydisulphate. The stoichiometric equations are as follows,

The final product in the oxidation of mucic acid was found to be trihydroxyglutaric acid (2), recognised by paper chromatography. In the case of benzilic acid, the final compound was identified as benzophenone. It was tested at different intervals of time during experiments and confirmed by isolating it as its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative, m.p. 236°.

Mechanism: The following mechanism seems reasonable,

Similarly,

Also,

Similarly,

Applying steady state treatment for the radicals $\dot{\text{O}}\text{H}$, Ag^{2+} , $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ and $\dot{\text{C}}\text{OOH}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\frac{d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} &= KK_2[\text{Ag}^+][\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \\
 &+ K_6[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] - \frac{KK_3}{K_5}[\text{Ag}^+] \\
 &\quad \text{(where, } K = K_1 / -K_1) \\
 &= 2KK_2[\text{Ag}^+][\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \\
 &= K'[\text{Ag}^+][\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]
 \end{aligned}$$

This relation narrates the salient features of the kinetic study to show the first order dependence on $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$ at constant $[\text{Ag}^+]$, and independence to [acid].

Discussion

As most of the workers have recently suggested, during Ag^+ catalysed oxidation process of the substrates by $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ ion, Ag^{2+} appears to be the reacting species. As per our study of the oxidation of the substituted acids (M.A. and B.A.), it is observed that the oxidation involves two distinct types of reactions, viz. (i) evolution of CO_2 indicating fission of C-C bond, and (ii) formation of keto group (as in case of B.A.) and CHO group which finally changes into COOH group (as in case

of M.A.). Thus in case of both the acids, the reaction deals with oxidative decarboxylation. The formation of $\dot{\text{C}}\text{OOH}$ and H^+ is the main factor while the free radical $\dot{\text{C}}\text{OOH}$ gives rise to CO_2 when attacked by $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and SO_4^- . It is evident that the reaction follows a radical mechanism which is supported by the fact that a radical scavenger, allyl acetate inhibits the speed of the reaction, the decrease in the rate by addition of $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ allyl acetate being 13.4 and 17.7% for M.A. and B.A., respectively.

The Ag^{I} catalysed oxidation of mucic acid is slow and its oxidation without the catalyst Ag^{I} appears to be difficult, while uncatalysed oxidation of B.A. is possible at 35° . The plots of k vs $[\text{AgNO}_3]$ show straight lines giving equations,

$$K = 2 \times 10^{-8} - 10C_{\text{Ag}^+} \quad (\text{in M.A.})$$

$$K = 23.3 \times 10^{-8} + 7.69C_{\text{Ag}^+} \quad (\text{in B.A.})$$

as represented in Fig. 4. This indicates that Ag^{II}

Fig. 4. Plot of $[\text{AgNO}_3]$ vs $\log k$. (○) M.A., and (●) B.A.

effects quicker formation of $\dot{\text{C}}\text{OOH}$ when there is smaller number of CHOH groups.

This finding is in agreement with the results obtained by Sen Gupta *et al.*¹⁰.

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